

Appendix 1.1: The indicative lists of economic values of nature's contributions to people (NCP) in Africa as presented in **Figure SPM.2** was extracted from the references listed below. They are grouped per sub-region, unit of analysis and NCP.

Sub-region	Ecosystem unit of analysis	NCP	Reference
North Africa	Inland surface waters and water bodies	Fishery value added	de Graaf, G., & Garibaldi, L. (2014). The value of African fisheries. Retrieved from http://www.fao.org/3/a-i3917e.pdf
	Tropical and subtropical dry and humid forests	Timber production	Daly, H. H. (2016). Assessment of the socio-economic value of the goods and services provided by Mediterranean forest ecosystems: Critical and comparative analysis of studies conducted in Algeria, Lebanon, Morocco, Tunisia and Turkey. Retrieved from http://www.fao.org/3/a-i6117e.pdf
	Marine and coastal areas	Carbon sequestration	Canu, D. M., Ghermandi, A., Nunes, P. A. L. D., Lazzari, P., Cossarini, G., & Solidoro, C. (2015). Estimating the value of carbon sequestration ecosystem services in the Mediterranean Sea: An ecological economics approach. <i>Global Environmental Change</i> , 32, 87–95. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2015.02.008
		Fishery value added	FAO FISHSTAT. (2017). Fisheries and aquaculture software. FishStat Plus–Universal software for fishery statistical time series. In FAO Fisheries and Aquaculture Department. Rome. Updated 14 September 2017.
East Africa and adjacent islands	Mangrove	Mangrove coastal protection	Mclean, B., Klaus, R., & Failler, P. (2017). Inputs for the design of an EU strategic approach to the coastal and marine biodiversity in Africa, Eastern and Southern Africa–Western Indian Ocean. <i>Larger than Whales</i> . Brussel: B4Life Programme.
	Inland surface waters and water bodies	Fishery value added	de Graaf, G., & Garibaldi, L. (2014). The value of African fisheries. Retrieved from http://www.fao.org/3/a-i3917e.pdf
	Tropical and subtropical savannas and grasslands	Erosion protection	Emerton, L. (1998). Djibouti biodiversity–economic assessment. IUCN, Gland, Switzerland.
	Tropical and subtropical dry and humid forests	Carbon sequestration	Emerton, L., & Muramira, E. (1999). Uganda biodiversity–economic assessment. Gland, Switzerland: IUCN.
		Bioprospecting	Emerton, L., & Muramira, E. (1999). Uganda biodiversity–economic assessment. Gland, Switzerland: IUCN.
	Marine and coastal areas	Carbon sequestration	Mclean, B., Klaus, R., & Failler, P. (2017). Inputs for the design of an EU strategic approach to the coastal and marine biodiversity in Africa, Eastern and Southern Africa–Western Indian Ocean. <i>Larger than Whale</i> . Brussels: B4Life Programme.
		Fishery value added	Mclean, B., Klaus, R., & Failler, P. (2017). Inputs for the design of an EU strategic approach to the coastal and marine biodiversity in Africa, Eastern and Southern Africa–Western Indian Ocean. <i>Larger than Whales</i> . Brussels: B4Life Programme.
	Deserts and drylands	Food production	Barrow, E., & Mogaka, H. (2007). Kenya's drylands: Wastelands or an undervalued national economic resource. Nairobi, Kenya: IUCN.
Southern Africa	Inland surface waters and water bodies	Fishery value added	de Graaf, G., & Garibaldi, L. (2014). The value of African fisheries. Retrieved from http://www.fao.org/3/a-i3917e.pdf

	Marine and coastal areas	Fishery value added	Klaus, R., Failler, P., & McClean, B. (2017). Inputs for the design of an EU strategic approach to the coastal and marine biodiversity in Africa, North Eastern Africa–Red Sea and Gulf of Aden. Larger than whales. Brussels: B4Life Programme.
	Tropical and subtropical savannas and grasslands	Recreation value	de Wit, M., & Blignaut, J. N. (2006). Monetary valuation of the grasslands in South Africa: Making the case for the value of ecosystem goods and services provided in the grassland. Retrieved from http://biodiversityadvisor.sanbi.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/07/2006deWit_Background-InfoRep5_Strategic-Monetary-valuation.pdf
Central Africa	Mangrove	Mangrove coastal protection	de Graaf, G., & Garibaldi, L. (2014). The value of African fisheries. Retrieved from http://www.fao.org/3/a-i3917e.pdf
	Inland surface waters and water bodies	Fishery value added	Failler, P., Klaus, R., & Mclean, B. (2017b). Inputs for the design of an EU strategic approach to the coastal and marine biodiversity in Africa, Western, Central and Southern Africa–Eastern Atlantic Ocean. Larger than Whales. Brussels: B4Life Programme.
	Tropical and subtropical dry and humid forests	Carbon sequestration	Yaron, G. (2001). Forest, plantation crops or small-scale agriculture? An economic analysis of alternative land use options in the Mount Cameroon Area. <i>Journal of Environmental Planning and Management</i> , 44(1), 85–108. https://doi.org/10.1080/09640560123194
		Timber value added	Yaron, G. (2001). Forest, plantation crops or small-scale agriculture? An economic analysis of alternative land use options in the Mount Cameroon Area. <i>Journal of Environmental Planning and Management</i> , 44(1), 85–108. https://doi.org/10.1080/09640560123194
	Marine and coastal areas	Fishery value added	Failler, P., Klaus, R., & Mclean, B. (2017a). Inputs for the design of an EU strategic approach to the coastal and marine biodiversity in Africa, synthesis. Brussels: B4Life Programme.
West Africa	Mangrove	Mangrove coastal protection	Acharya, G., & Barbier, E .B. (2000). Valuing groundwater recharge through agricultural production in the Hadejia-Nguru wetlands in northern Nigeria. <i>Agricultural Economics</i> , 22(3), 247–259. https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-5150(99)00054-7
	Inland surface waters and water bodies	Water purification	Failler, P., Binet, A., Doumbouya, A., & Sall, A. (2012). Évaluation de la valeur socio-économique des écosystèmes marins et côtiers des Aires marines protégées de l’Afrique de l’Ouest, Résumé. Dakar, Senegal: Programme RAMPAO.
	Marine and coastal areas	Fishery value added	Failler, P. (2016). Addendum of UNEP report on the socioeconomics of the West, Central and Southern African coastal communities: A synthesis of studies regarding large marine ecosystems. Nairobi, Kenya: UNEP.
		Carbon sequestration	Failler, P. (2016). Addendum of UNEP report on the socioeconomics of the West, Central and Southern African coastal communities: A synthesis of studies regarding large marine ecosystems. Nairobi, Kenya: UNEP.